

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetics

Testing the predicted performance of recombinant inbred lines in rice using triple test cross (TTC) design, Basic Generations, and F₃ families

A. L. T. Perera and S. Palihawadana, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Peradeniya, Sri Lanka; and M. J. Lawrence, School of Biological Sciences, University of Birmingham, UK

We predicted the performance of recombinant inbred lines of three crosses by obtaining estimates of m (midparent value) and D (additive genetic variance) from TTC design, Basic Generations, and genetic parameters from F₃ families (Table 1). We only discuss 1,000-grain weight and panicles per plant out of several characters studied.

From each of the crosses, 90 inbred lines were produced using single-seed descent procedure. We measured the characters that we predicted.

The actual and predicted values were very close (Table 2). In cross A, the actual percentage of lines produced was

Table 1. Estimates of m and D obtained from TTC and basic generation families and from F₃ families for 1000-grain wt and panicles per plant for crosses A, D, and E.

Source	1000-grain wt (g)			Panicles (no./plant)		
	A	D	E	A	D	E
			\hat{m}			
TTC and Basic Generation	25.6	29.4	40.1	21.3	16.6	17.5
F ₃	26.5	28.8	29.3	25.8	18.9	19.7
			\hat{D}			
TTC and Basic Generation	6.0	2.8	4.9	19.6	19.2	14.9
F ₃	3.9	4.4	3.3	15.2	14.4	5.7

Table 2. Predictions (% better than better parent) and recombinant inbred lines actually produced from crosses A, D, and E.

Item	1000-grain wt (g)			Panicles (no./plant)		
	A	D	E	A	D	E
TTC predictions (%)	13	3	10	5	49	4
F ₃ predictions (%)	17	3.8	0.7	24	41	3
Lines produced (%)	13	12	13	29	20	24

very close to the predicted values. In cross D, the actual percentage of lines produced in both cases was much closer to the F₃ predictions than to the TTC predictions. In cross E, for both characters, more superior inbred lines were produced than predicted.

The results indicate that the two sets of predictions agree reasonably well.

The actual number of superior inbred lines produced agreed the best with F₃ predictions. F₃ families, which are grown for all crosses in rice breeding programs, can be used as an accurate alternate source of genetic parameters to predict the outcome of crosses early in breeding programs. □

Breeding methods

Effect of maltose and gelling agent on protoplast culture response in indica rice

E. S. Ella and F. J. Zapata, IRRI

Indica rices have a relatively lower response to protoplast culture than japonica rices. We manipulated the culture medium to improve the plating efficiency of suspension-derived protoplasts of IR72.

Cell suspension was initiated from mature seed and maintained in liquid N₆ medium with 5 mM proline, 2 mg 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D)/liter

Table 1. Effect of osmotic concentration of maltose on the viability of cells in culture.

Maltose (% wt/vol)	Duration (d) of protoplast viability in culture ^a
9	4.8 d
11	8.5 c
13	>28.0 a
15	13.8 b

^aAv of 4 replications over time. Mean separation by DMRT at 5% level. One replication consisted of 3 plates with 1.5×10^5 protoplasts per plate.

and 30 g maltose/liter. Protoplasts were isolated from 5- to 6-mo-old cell suspension and plated in 1.5 ml medium

Table 2. Effect of type of gelling agent on the plating efficiency of IR72 protoplasts.

Gelling agent	Plating efficiency ^a (%)
Agarose VII	0.67 b
Sea plaque agarose	0.88 a

^aPlating efficiency = $\frac{\text{no. of colony-producing protoplasts}}{\text{total no. of protoplasts plated}} \times 100$ (%)

Av of 4 replications over time. Mean separation by DMRT at 5% level. One replication consisted of 3 plates with 1.5×10^5 protoplasts per plate.

solidified with 6 g agarose VII (Sigma)/liter at 1×10^5 protoplasts/ml. The gel was bathed in 4-ml liquid medium with

nurse cells (20 mg/ml). Suspension cultures of Oc cell line from Dr. K. Syono of the University of Tokyo were used as nurse cells. Nurse cells were removed after 10 d and the liquid was replaced with the same amount of fresh medium. Under the inverted microscope, the cultures were observed periodically for colony formation. The number of colony-producing protoplasts was recorded 4 wk after plating.

Semisolid N₆ medium consisting of 0.6% agarose VII wt/vol and 2 mg 2,4-D/

liter was tested with sucrose and maltose as the C source. The protoplasts remained viable (with cytoplasmic streaming and changes in shape) for a longer time (3-5 d) in maltose than in sucrose (1-2 d).

We used maltose as the C source when we tested series of semisolid N₆ media. Maltose (13% wt/vol) was found to be the best osmotic concentration for protoplast culture (Table 1). Many cellular divisions and some colonies were

observed 28 d after plating.

To evaluate the efficiency of colony formation, the N₆ medium with 13% maltose was modified using 0.6% agarose VII and 0.5% sea plaque agarose. Both media gave about the same hardness. The plating efficiency was higher in medium with sea plaque agarose (Table 2).

So far, initial attempts to regenerate green plants from protoplast-derived calli have produced only green points. □

Low-light-adapted restorers of different maturity durations for hybrid rice breeding

K. S. Murty, S. K. Dey, P. Swain, and M. J. Baig, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 753006, India

Low light levels during the critical reproductive and ripening phases adversely affect rice productivity. Heterotic hybrid combinations with restorers adapted to low light can improve productivity during the wet season (WS).

We studied the low light adaptability of 39 recently purified restorers of elite rice varieties with maturity durations of early (111-120 d), early to medium (121-130 d), medium (131-140 d), and late (more than 141 d). Wooden screens shaded the plants in the field and provided 50% sunlight from 40 d after planting to harvest. Controls were maintained under normal sunlight (340 cal/cm² per d).

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design. Yield, total dry matter (TDM), and harvest index (HI) were recorded at harvest.

The low light reduced mean TDM by 63%, yield 75%, and HI 36% (see table). The extent of reduction, however, was least in the late-maturing group and most in the early to medium group. TDM, yield, and HI were high—specially under low light—iRtb 10, IR50 (early); Swarnaprabha, IR64 R (early to medium); IR19058-107-1, Vajram, ARC11353 (medium); and Jagannath and Mahsuri (late). These restorers also

The effect of low light (50% of normal) from 40 d after planting to harvest on yield, TDM, and HI of restorers with varying maturity durations. Cuttack, India, 1991 wet season.

Restorer	Yield (g/m ²)		TDM (g/m ²)		HI (%)	
	Light	Shade	Light	Shade	Light	Shade
Early (111-120 d)						
IR58	437	83	825	286	53	29
WGL3962	413	61	831	206	49	27
IR50	369	113	733	315	50	36
Ptb 10	347	202	669	452	52	45
IR50 R	342	91	701	280	48	32
Prasad	338	44	683	175	49	25
HKR120	334	77	773	303	42	26
IET6155	323	67	620	194	52	34
Semaigincha	320	77	760	233	55	33
IR339515-8-1-1	300	58	602	184	49	32
WGL 3935	256	36	635	194	40	17
IR22107-120-1	231	41	494	144	47	28
Early to medium (121-130 d)						
Swarnaprabha ^a	567	142	1167	481	49	28
IR64 R	392	102	936	350	41	30
Suweon 318	379	38	860	191	44	20
Tellahdmsa	368	32	786	208	49	15
HKR119	365	80	809	242	45	33
IR64	352	61	773	219	46	28
IR36	351	64	133	238	43	27
Suweon 332	338	48	727	198	46	25
Suweon 294	325	68	736	229	44	30
Pusa 702 R	321	74	683	248	47	31
Pusa 205 R	313	40	856	221	36	17
Suweon 325	261	36	590	157	44	23
Milyang 54	235	32	657	164	36	21
Ratna ^a	223	17	681	177	34	17
Medium (131-140 d)						
Vajram	560	150	1409	473	40	34
ARC11353	421	138	1027	488	40	26
IR54	363	111	1094	464	33	23
IR19058-107-1	337	158	1227	595	27	27
Indira ^a	257	56	1047	262	25	19
IR2731.5-145-1-3	257	86	937	470	26	19
Indrasan	249	86	581	289	43	28
IR4422-480-2-3-3	191	24	719	171	26	14
Late (more than 141 d)						
Jagannath	576	219	1366	656	42	33
Mahsuri	475	187	1283	677	37	27
Savitri	469	158	1447	679	49	32
Samalei	460	168	1419	601	32	28
Swama	433	186	1106	523	39	36
LSD (0.05)	162	58	226	129	11	ns
Means						
111-120 d	334	79	694	247	49	30
121-130 d	342	60	785	237	43	25
131-140 d	329	100	1005	401	33	24
>141 d	483	184	1324	627	40	36
General mean	355	90	871	3	2442	27

^aPartial restorer.